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A Review of Sociological, Individual and Psychological Crime Theories

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Abstract

This article is a thorough examination of the core principles underlying numerous crime theories, offering a complete explanation of these notions. The review commences by scrutinizing the definition of crime, the concept of guilt, and deviation. Following this, the discussion explores a range of societal, individual, psychological, and biological ideas pertaining to crime.

Sociological theories of crime place significant emphasis on the influence of societal circumstances in the development of criminal behavior. These theories encompass concepts such as the Broken Windows Theory and the Rational Choice Theory. Ideas of individual crime place emphasis on the correlation between culpability and personal choices and motivations. These ideas encompass several

approaches, such as the Classical School and Neo-Classical School. Psychological crime theories examine the psychological elements that contribute to criminal behavior, while also seeking to understand the underlying motivations and influences that drive individuals to engage in unlawful activities. Biological crime theories aim to examine the underlying biological factors contributing to criminal behavior.

The article comprehensively examines the etiology of criminal behavior, many categories of criminal acts, and the influential factors stemming from both societal and individual contexts that contribute to criminality.

Keywords : *Crime , Crime Theories , Sociological Crime Theories , Individual Crime Theories, Psychological crime theories*

INTRODUCTION

Crime is a subject of perpetual intrigue and extensive contemplation within the framework of human society. Crime is a social construct that is defined and delineated by societies. In order to maintain social order and uphold the principles of justice, societies employ punitive methods to address criminal behavior. Additionally, preventative measures are implemented to mitigate the occurrence of crimes within a given society. Nevertheless, the etiology of crime, its underlying causes, and the multifaceted influences on criminal behavior are inherently intricate. The comprehension and explication of this intricacy pose a significant obstacle for sociologists, psychologists, and legal professionals.

This article aims to explore several aspects of crime through an analysis of the notion of crime and crime theories. The scope of our review will be centered around three primary categories, namely sociological crime theories, individual crime theories, and psychological crime theories. These theoretical frameworks facilitate our comprehension of the underlying factors

contributing to criminal behavior and the diverse mechanisms through which it manifests, thereby shedding light on multiple dimensions of criminal activity.

Sociological theories pertaining to crime place significant emphasis on the influence of social elements in the genesis of criminal behavior, while also scrutinizing the social milieu within which crime manifests. While individual crime theories examine the correlation between crime and individual choices and motivations, psychological crime theories focus on the psychological roots of criminal behavior. Each of these theories provides a significant viewpoint in elucidating the etiology and dissemination of criminal behavior.

The primary objective of this essay is to enhance comprehension of the multifaceted nature of crime through a comprehensive analysis of its societal, individual, and psychological aspects. Additionally, this study will assess the impact of criminal activity on societal structure and legal frameworks, while also making valuable contributions to ongoing dialogues surrounding crime prevention strategies and the reintegration of offenders into society.

AIM

The primary objective of this article is to gain a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of criminal behavior and to critically analyze various theoretical frameworks that seek to explain the causes and dynamics of crime. The primary objective of this study is to enhance our comprehension of the phenomena of crime by conducting an in-depth analysis of social, individual, and psychological crime theories.

Initially, our attention is directed towards social theories pertaining to crime. These theories aim to elucidate the societal underpinnings of criminal behavior by highlighting the social milieu in which crime occurs and the influence of social determinants on the genesis of criminal acts. Subsequently, an analysis is conducted to explore the correlation between criminal activity and individual motivations and decisions through the examination of several individual crime theories. Psychological theories of crime provide valuable insights into the underlying psychological factors contributing to criminal behavior.

The objective of this article is to enhance comprehension about the intricacies of criminal behavior and to provide a scholarly contribution to the study of crime causation, repercussions, and prevention. This will be achieved through a comprehensive examination of many crime

theories, with each theory being analyzed in depth. Within this particular setting, an evaluation is conducted on the consequences of crime on social order and legal institutions by shedding light on various facets of criminal activity.

The methodology employed in this study was carefully designed and implemented to ensure accurate and reliable results.

The present investigation was conducted utilizing the procedures of literature review and source review. The researcher conducted a comprehensive review of academic publications, books, theses, and other scholarly resources pertaining to the relevant areas. The aforementioned sources facilitated the acquisition of information pertaining to diverse facets of crime theories. The review method was centered on addressing specific research inquiries, and the findings derived from this procedure are subsequently reported in this review paper.

FINDINGS

The scholarly literature presents varying perspectives on the ideas of deviation and crime, leading to a vigorous discourse over the classification of action as either a deviation or a crime. This classification is contingent upon whether the activity is deemed deviant solely by societal norms or also by legal statutes (Dolu, 2011; 2013). In the present context, the term "deviation" pertains to actions that transgress the established standards of a specific community or social group during a particular timeframe (Siegel, 2006: 4). Conversely, "crime" denotes conduct that contravenes legal regulations and necessitates punitive measures as prescribed by the criminal justice system (Yücel, 2003; Dolu, 2011). To enhance comprehension of this differentiation, it is imperative to underscore the fundamental disparities between deviation and criminality. Deviation encompasses actions that deviate from established social standards and are deemed atypical within a given community, whereas criminality pertains to activities that surpass the legal boundaries prescribed by the law (Thio et al., 2013). Hence, deviation is commonly regarded as a transgression of societal norms, while crime pertains to a transgression of legal norms established by criminal law. According to scholarly sources, deviation is commonly understood as the act of surpassing widely accepted views (Thio et al., 2013). Deviant behavior, on the other hand, can be described as an exceptional and unforeseen type of action inside a certain society or group (Palmer and Humphrey, 1990: vii). Both notions pertain to circumstances that deviate from the established normative framework designed to uphold social

order and sustain its ongoing stability. Deviation can be understood as behavior that deviates from societal norms and is generally disapproved by the majority. On the other hand, criminality is characterized by activity that violates legal regulations and necessitates legal consequences. Nevertheless, it is important to note that not all instances of deviation may be classified as criminal acts, and conversely, not all criminal acts can be categorized as deviations. Deviance and criminality share certain qualities while also exhibiting distinct variances. The phenomenon of social change, characterized by the gradual transformation of societal norms and values, has the potential to exert an impact on the conceptualization and delineation of deviant behavior and criminal acts.

The notions of crime and guilt have garnered considerable interest among individuals throughout the existence of human society. The origins of systematic explanations of crime and guilt can be traced back to the 18th century when Italian lawyer Cesare first introduced these concepts. The origins can be traced back to the contributions made by Beccaria. In his renowned publication "On Crimes and Punishments," Beccaria (2010) underscored the social nature of crime through an analysis of its causes and the operational dynamics of the penal system.

The work of Beccaria represents a significant advancement in the pursuit of a rational comprehension of the underlying factors contributing to criminal behavior, as well as the subsequent implementation of a legalistic framework for the administration of justice in penalizing offenders. According to Beccaria, criminal behavior arises from individual decision-making and cognitive processes. He advocated for a legal system that assumes a fair and preventive role in the punishment of offenders.

During the mid-20th century, there was a notable shift towards a more scientific approach to studying crime and criminality, which was mostly conducted within a positivist paradigm. During this time frame, scholarly investigations were undertaken to examine the juxtaposition between individuals engaged in criminal activities and the impact of various social conditions on their behavior. The positivist perspective posits that crime and delinquency are influenced by various social, economic, and psychological variables.

By the onset of the 21st century, the field of social sciences has exhibited a notable emphasis on the subject matter of criminal behavior. Numerous theoretical frameworks have been established in order to comprehend the factors that influence criminal behavior and to elucidate

the relationship between crime and punishment. Within this domain, scholarly investigations have primarily focused on two fundamental paradigms: classical and positivist.

The classical school of criminology posits that criminal behavior is primarily driven by the rational decision-making processes of individuals. According to the perspective of this educational institution, individuals who engage in criminal activities possess cognitive faculties and will, actively making a conscious choice to perpetrate the unlawful act. Based on classical theory, individuals who engage in criminal behavior engage in a process of risk assessment, wherein they analyze the potential consequences and penalties associated with their actions before deciding to commit a crime. Therefore, it is imperative to underscore the importance of implementing deterrent and equitable sanctions as a means of crime prevention (Beccaria, 2010).

In contrast, the positivist school posits that criminal behavior is influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic variables experienced by the individual. As per the institution's perspective, crime can be attributed to several elements encompassing social, economic, and psychological dimensions. Criminal behavior is believed to be influenced by a multitude of elements, including but not limited to the social environment, familial structures, economic conditions, and individual traits. Positivist theories endeavor to enhance the efficacy of crime-fighting techniques through the application of scientific methodologies to investigate the underlying reasons of criminal behavior (Siegel, 2006).

Currently, there is an ongoing and dynamic process of research and theoretical advancements in the field of crime and criminality. The issue of crime and criminality in societies undergoes transformations in response to shifts in social, economic, and political dynamics. Research conducted on the etiology and ramifications of criminal behavior plays a pivotal role in advancing the formulation of enhanced strategies and interventions aimed at addressing and mitigating crime within societies. The topic of crime and criminality remains a subject of multidisciplinary examination and holds significant importance as scholars strive to achieve more comprehensive and meaningful outcomes. Sociological theories pertaining to crime aim to elucidate the origins and proliferation of criminal behavior via the analysis of diverse social dynamics and structures. The aforementioned theories hold significant importance in comprehending the dynamics of social order and the processes of social control. In any given community, it is a typical occurrence for certain behaviors to be outlawed and thereafter subject to legal punishments. According to Dönmezer (1981: 72), criminal behavior is influenced by

societal circumstances. In societal contexts, it can be argued that the collective environment plays a role in shaping the propensity for criminal behavior, although the responsibility for the actual commission of such acts lies with the individual. The etiology of criminal behavior can be attributed to social and legal systems rather than solely to the individual offender. According to Yücel (2003: 53), Without a question, sociologically oriented perspectives offer the most comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to criminal behavior. The concept of crime is socially built and defined, making it difficult for any discipline to evaluate the issue as effectively as the field of sociology (Heidensohn, 1989). The assertion that criminal behavior is influenced by social interaction and societal factors, therefore positioning sociologists as the most suitable experts to elucidate crime, underscores the significance of utilizing the discipline of sociology to study criminal phenomena (Siegel, 2006: 178). The comprehensive understanding of crime, deviant or criminal behavior, and the motivating factors behind individuals' engagement in criminal activities need the incorporation of sociological perspectives, as theoretical frameworks that disregard this aspect are insufficient in their explanatory capacity. The sociological perspective elucidates the dynamic elements of human behavior that give rise to criminal activities, attributing them to societal transformations and other social circumstances. Additionally, this perspective, as articulated by Mills (Carrabine et al., 2009: 5), aids individuals in enhancing their efficacy as members of society. Crime can be understood as a result of the social environment, as viewed through a sociological lens. According to İçli (1994: 67), this approach posits that it is not the individual criminal who is afflicted with illness, but rather the society itself.

The historical progression of the sociological analysis of crime was elucidated by Sutherland and Cressey (1978). The study commenced with the school of cartography criminology, which posited that issues pertaining to crime and delinquency were an inherent outcome of social and geographical circumstances. Subsequently, it progressed to the sociological-socialist school. During the mid-19th century, there was a significant increase in the prevalence of methodologies that examined crime through the lens of the social context.

The school of cartographic criminology was established by Adolphe Quetelet, a Belgian mathematician, and André-Michel Guerry, a French jurist. The educational institution conducted an inquiry into the correlation between criminal activity and societal variables through the application of empirical methodologies. Based on an analysis of crime statistics, this study examines the impact of several elements, including gender, age, season, climate,

poverty, and wealth, on the population. Additionally, it investigates the influence of social factors on individuals' propensity to engage in criminal behavior.

For instance, previous research has established a correlation between social elements, including season, climate, demographic characteristics, and poverty, and their impact on the development of criminal conduct (Dönmezer, 1981; İçli, 1994a; Siegel, 2006; Dolu, 2011).

The founders of the positivist school were instrumental in establishing the French school of crime sociology as a critical framework. The school posited that social issues are the underlying cause of criminal behavior. Alexander Lacassagne, a prominent intellectual, ascribed the etiology of criminal behavior to social determinants rather than human causes. According to his perspective, social variables are the underlying causes that lead individuals to engage in criminal behavior. The aforementioned concept is articulated through the theory posited by Dönmezer (1981) that "each society possesses the criminals it merits."

Gabriel Tarde has espoused a comparable methodology. Tarde argues that criminal activity is not just attributed to the individual offender, but also bears societal responsibility. According to his perspective, crime can be acquired as a learned behavior and is influenced by societal norms and practices. The acquisition of criminal behavior is predicated upon the principle of imitation, wherein individuals mold their conduct in alignment with societal standards (Adler et al., 2018).

According to Sutherland and Cressey (1978), it is possible that individuals engaging in criminal behavior may be influenced by the actions of others within society.

The aforementioned data demonstrate a strong correlation between crime and sociological and societal issues. The etiology and dissemination of criminal behavior are influenced by various social and environmental factors. Hence, it is imperative to use a holistic approach in addressing crime, encompassing not just human determinants but also societal and environmental elements. The comprehension of crime's origins and the implementation of successful interventions are greatly facilitated by the utilization of sociological viewpoints and scientific methodologies. Recognizing that crime is not solely attributable to individual criminals, but is also influenced by societal and environmental factors, is a crucial initial measure in formulating more efficacious approaches to address crime. Hence, it is imperative to sustain ongoing study and investigations pertaining to crime and delinquency.

Historical Development of Crime Theories

Crime theories provide a diverse range of viewpoints that facilitate the comprehension of the multifaceted nature of criminal activities. These theories contribute to the development of society's crime prevention policies by offering a comprehensive comprehension of the underlying causes, origins, and consequences of criminal behavior. It is imperative to recognize that crime encompasses not just human behavior, but also exhibits strong interconnections with social dynamics, economic circumstances, psychological influences, and structural components.

These theories seek to mitigate the proliferation of criminal activities by examining the fundamental factors that contribute to criminal behavior. Additionally, its objective is to design efficacious approaches for crime prevention and the rehabilitation of offenders. Gaining insight into the impact of criminal activities on the societal structure facilitates the development of enhanced and enduring strategies in combating crime and upholding social cohesion.

Theories of crime underscore the notion that effectively addressing crime necessitates not just the implementation of sanctions, but also a comprehensive study and resolution of the underlying causal factors. When formulating ways to combat crime within society, using the insights provided by these theories can facilitate the implementation of a more equitable, efficient, and human-centered strategy.

Sociological crime theories encompass theoretical frameworks that aim to examine the influence of social factors on crime and provide explanations for crime as a social phenomenon. Instead than attributing crime solely to individual qualities or psychological elements, these theories prioritize the examination of social dynamics, including social structure, social interactions, economic conditions, and cultural influences.

Crime theories are categorized according to several perspectives that seek to comprehend the reasons and origins of criminal behavior. The primary objective of this differentiation is to strive for a more comprehensive comprehension by analyzing the phenomena of crime from a multidimensional perspective. The multifaceted nature of crime has prompted scholars and researchers from various academic fields to endeavor in elucidating its diverse facets through the exploration of distinct theoretical frameworks.

Sociological theories primarily center their attention on the various dimensions of crime that exert an influence on social structure, norms, values, and social connections. These theories examine the dissemination of crime within society, the correlation between social disparities and structural elements with crime, and the efficacy of social control systems. Social theories seek to comprehend the manner in which crime is influenced by the intricate interplay and organizational frameworks of society.

Psychological theories aim to explore the mechanisms underlying the occurrence of crime at the individual level, as well as the ways in which individuals may engage in criminal behavior as a result of various psychological circumstances. These theories explore the impact of internal elements, such as people's personality patterns, psychological disorders, traumas, and motivations, on the likelihood of engaging in criminal behavior. Psychological theories establish a connection between the etiology of criminal behavior and the cognitive and affective processes of the individual.

In contrast, biological theories delve into the examination of the correlation between criminal behavior and biological elements. These theories propose that crime propensity may be influenced by genetic, neurological, and biological features. Biological theories of crime seek to elucidate the biological mechanisms that contribute to criminal behavior by investigating the interplay between genetic predisposition, brain structure, and hormone influences.

The rationale behind these differentiations stems from the intricate and multifaceted nature of crime. Various theories endeavor to offer a more comprehensive viewpoint by placing emphasis on distinct facets of criminal behavior. Each theoretical framework provides a substantial contribution towards comprehending the underlying factors that contribute to criminal behavior and formulating effective ways for combating crime. The presence of diverse crime theories has significant importance in comprehending various dimensions of criminal behavior and devising efficacious social interventions.

The notions of crime and guilt have garnered significant interest among individuals throughout the existence of human society. However, the origins of systematic explanations of crime and guilt can be traced back to the 18th century when Italian lawyer Cesare Beccaria made significant contributions in this field. The origins can be traced back to the contributions made by Beccaria. Beccaria (2010) extensively examined the origins of criminal behavior and the operational mechanisms of the prison system in his renowned publication "On Crimes and

Punishments." He notably underscored the social nature of crime, emphasizing its status as a collective phenomenon.

Beccaria's contribution represents a significant advancement in comprehending the underlying factors contributing to criminal behavior, as well as the subsequent implementation of a legalistic framework for the administration of justice in penalizing offenders. Beccaria claimed that criminal behavior arises from individual volition and cognitive processes, advocating for a legal system that assumes a just and preventive function in the punishment of offenders.

During the mid-19th century, there was a shift towards a more scientific approach to the study of crime and criminality, which occurred within the framework of positivism. During this time frame, scholarly investigations were undertaken to examine the juxtaposition of individuals engaged in criminal activities and the impact of various societal circumstances on their behavior. The positivist perspective posits that crime and delinquency are influenced by various social, economic, and psychological variables.

During the 20th century, the field of social sciences dedicated considerable attention to the phenomenon of criminality. Numerous theoretical frameworks have been established in order to comprehend the factors that contribute to criminal behavior and to elucidate the relationship between crime and punishment. This subject has been extensively explored through the lens of two fundamental schools of thought: classical and positivist.

The classical school of thought posits that crime is rooted in the logical decision-making process of individuals. As per the perspective of this educational institution, individuals who engage in criminal activities possess cognitive abilities and will, actively making a conscious decision to perpetrate the unlawful act. Based on classical theory, individuals who engage in criminal behavior engage in a rational decision-making process wherein they assess the potential risks and consequences associated with their actions, including the likelihood of facing punitive measures and sanctions. Therefore, it is highlighted that the implementation of deterrent and equitable penalties is crucial in order to mitigate criminal activity. In contrast, proponents of the positivist school think that crime is influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic variables experienced by the individual. As per the institution's perspective, crime can be attributed to several elements encompassing social, economic, and psychological dimensions. Criminal behavior is believed to be influenced by a range of elements, including the social environment, family structures, economic conditions, and personal qualities. Positivist ideas seek to enhance

the efficacy of crime-fighting techniques through the utilization of scientific methodologies to investigate the underlying reasons of criminal behavior.

The primary distinctions between the classical and positivist schools pertain to the comprehension of crime causation and the explication of criminal conduct. The classical school posits that criminal behavior is contingent upon an individual's exercise of free will and rational decision-making, whereas the positivist school contends that crime is influenced by various social and psychological elements.

The classical and positivist schools of criminology present distinct theoretical frameworks for comprehending the underlying factors contributing to crime and criminal conduct. The classical school posits that criminal behavior arises from an individual's exercise of free will and rational decision-making, whereas the positivist school contends that crime is influenced by various social, economic, and psychological variables. These various viewpoints focus distinct emphasis on the origins and etiology of criminal behavior.

Classical theories place significant emphasis on the notion that criminal activity arises from the deliberate choice made by the offender, hence advocating for the imposition of punitive measures upon the criminal. These ideas claim that deterrent consequences are efficacious in combating crime and underscore the notion that criminal behavior is associated with human inclinations and decision-making.

In contrast, positivist views contend that criminal behavior is influenced by social and psychological circumstances, positing that individuals do not possess complete agency over their propensity for criminality. These ideas claim that enhancing social structure and environmental conditions plays a crucial role in combating crime and emphasize the need of scientific research in comprehending the fundamental reasons of criminal behavior.

The examination of both of these educational institutions in conjunction might enhance the overall comprehension of the issue of crime and delinquency, as well as facilitate the development of more efficacious measures in combating criminal activities. Classical views postulate a connection between crime and individual decision-making, whereas positivist ideas elucidate a correlation between crime and social and environmental causes.

The examination of crime causation at both individual and social levels, as facilitated by positivist theories, has played a significant role in the advancement of more efficacious crime-

fighting tactics. The inclusion of scientific studies on crime and delinquency has facilitated the adoption of a more cognizant and empirically grounded approach within societies to combat criminal activities.

Currently, there is an ongoing and dynamic process of research and theoretical advancements in the field of crime and criminality. The manner in which societies contend with crime and criminality is subject to modification in response to shifts in social, economic, and political dynamics. Research focused on the etiology and ramifications of criminal behavior plays a pivotal role in advancing the formulation of enhanced strategies and interventions aimed at addressing and mitigating crime within societies. The topic of crime and criminality remains a subject of interdisciplinary inquiry and holds significant importance as scholars strive to achieve more comprehensive and meaningful outcomes.

According to Sutherland and Cressey (1978: 60), the sociological analysis of crime originated from the cartographic criminology school and subsequently evolved through the sociological-socialist school. During the 19th century, there was a notable proliferation of views that commonly assessed crime as a product of the social milieu. The proponents of the school of cartographic criminology, alternatively referred to as the geographical school, assert that crime and delinquency issues arise as an inevitable outcome of social and geographical circumstances. Among the pioneers of this perspective was Adolphe Quetelet, a Belgian mathematician who is recognized as one of the early social criminologists. Quetelet and the French jurist André-Michel Guerry. Under the paradigm of this particular approach, researchers explored the correlation between criminal behavior and societal elements through the application of rigorous scientific methodologies.

Based on an analysis of crime statistics, this study examines the influence of many elements, including gender, age, season, climate, poverty, and wealth, on the population. Additionally, it investigates the impact of social factors on individuals' propensity to engage in criminal behavior. It has been established that various social element, including season, climate, demographic characteristics, and poverty, are interconnected with crime and have an impact on the development of criminal behavior (Dönmezer, 1981; İçli, 1994a; Siegel, 2006; Dolu, 2011).

The French school of crime sociology emerged as a critical perspective within the positivist school, spearheaded by influential figures such as Alexander Lacassagne and Gabriel Tarde. This school of thought arose in opposition to the Italian anthropology of crime. The

establishment of this educational institution drew inspiration from the intellectual contributions of prominent philosophers such as Montesquieu, Rousseau, and Locke (Bal, 2013). According to Alexander Lacassagne, social elements are posited as the causative agents behind criminal behavior. While it is true that individual characteristics can sometimes play a role in crime causation, their influence is generally considered to be secondary and less significant when compared to social causes. Lacassagne posits that individuals' criminal tendencies are mostly influenced by social circumstances, asserting the notion that "each society harbors criminals commensurate with its own characteristics" (Dönmezer, 1981).

According to Bal (2013), Gabriel Tarde posits that criminal activity is a significant issue that necessitates accountability not only from the individual perpetrator but also from society as a whole. Good afternoon, Lombroso. The individual in question refutes the psycho-biological stereotypes as a foundation for the theory of guilt, contending that criminal behavior is acquired through a process akin to the acquisition of valid survival skills by ordinary individuals. Adler et al. (2018) suggest that the acquisition of criminal behavior is predicated upon the principle of imitation, wherein individuals mold their conduct in accordance with societal norms. According to Sutherland and Cressey (1978), those who engage in theft or seek to commit murder may be observed copying certain behaviors exhibited across society.

Sociological Theories of Crime

Sociological theories pertaining to crime aim to elucidate the origins and proliferation of criminal behavior via the analysis of diverse social dynamics and structures. These theories hold significant importance in comprehending the dynamics of social order and the processes of social control. Throughout history, it can be observed that every civilization has implemented prohibitions on specific behaviors and established corresponding criminal consequences. Crimes were influenced by societal circumstances, as stated by Dönmezer (1981: 72).

In the context of criminal behavior, it can be argued that societal factors contribute to the predisposition for crime, whereas human agency ultimately determines the decision to engage in criminal acts. The etiology of criminal behavior can be attributed to social and legal systems rather than solely to the individual offender. According to Yücel (2003: 53), Without a question, sociologically oriented perspectives offer the most comprehensive understanding of the underlying factors contributing to criminal behavior. Heidensohn (1989: 2-3) argues that due to

its socially created and defined nature, the issue of crime has been most effectively examined by the field of sociology. According to Siegel (2006: 178), criminal behavior is influenced by social interaction and social dynamics. As a result, sociologists are well-positioned to provide the most comprehensive explanations for crime. This underscores the significance of studying crime through the lens of sociology as a scientific discipline. The phenomena of crime, deviant or criminal behavior, and the underlying motivations that drive individuals to engage in illegal activities cannot be comprehensively explained by theoretical approaches that neglect the sociological perspective. The sociological perspective elucidates the dynamic elements of human behavior that give rise to criminal activities, attributing them to societal transformations and other social circumstances. Additionally, this perspective, as articulated by Mills (Carrabine et al., 2009: 5), aids individuals in enhancing their efficacy as members of society. Crime can be understood as a consequence of the social environment when viewed through a sociological lens. According to İçli (1994: 67), the perspective under consideration posits that it is the society, rather than the criminal, which is afflicted with illness. Sutherland and Cressey (1978: 60) assert that the study of crime from a sociological perspective originated with the cartographic criminology school and subsequently progressed with the sociological-socialist school. During the 19th century, there was a notable proliferation of methodologies that predominantly assessed crime as a product of the societal context. The proponents of the discipline known as cartographic criminology, alternatively referred to as the geographical school, assert that crime and delinquency issues arise as an inevitable outcome of prevailing social and geographical circumstances. Among the pioneers of this field was Adolphe Quetelet, a Belgian mathematician who is recognized as one of the early social criminologists. Quetelet and the French jurist André-Michel Guerry. Under the paradigm of this particular approach, researchers examined the correlation between criminal behavior and societal variables through the application of rigorous scientific methodologies.

Based on an analysis of crime statistics, this study examines the influence of many elements, including gender, age, season, climate, poverty, and wealth, on the population. Additionally, it investigates the impact of social factors on individuals' propensity to engage in criminal behavior. It has been established that various social element, including season, climate, demographic characteristics, and poverty, are interconnected with crime and have an impact on the development of criminal behavior (Dönmezer, 1981; İçli, 1994a; Siegel, 2006; Dolu, 2011).

The French school of crime sociology emerged as a critical perspective within the positivist school, spearheaded by notable figures such as Alexander Lacassagne and Gabriel Tarde. This

school of thought arose in opposition to the Italian anthropology of crime. The establishment of this educational institution drew inspiration from the philosophical contributions of renowned intellectuals such as Montesquieu, Rousseau, and Locke (Bal, 2013). According to Alexander Lacassagne, social elements are identified as the causative agents of criminal behavior. While it is true that individual characteristics can sometimes play a role in crime causation, their influence is generally considered to be secondary and less significant when compared to social causes. According to Lacassagne, criminal behavior is mostly influenced by social variables, suggesting that each culture possesses criminals that are a reflection of their own characteristics and values (Dönmezer, 1981). Gabriel Tarde posits a similar viewpoint, contending that criminal conduct is a pervasive issue for which both the individual perpetrator and society at large have responsibility. According to Bal (2013), Good afternoon, Lombroso. The individual in question refutes the psycho-biological assumptions that underpin the notion of guilt, positing instead that criminal behavior is acquired through a process akin to the acquisition of valid survival skills by ordinary individuals. Adler et al. (2018) assert that the acquisition of criminal behavior is contingent upon the concept of imitation, wherein individuals mold their conduct in accordance with societal norms. According to Sutherland and Cressey (1978), individuals who engage in theft or seek to commit murder may be engaging in behavior that mimics certain societal influences.

The French school of crime sociology places significant emphasis on the intricate relationship between crime and social structure and interactions. It posits that crime cannot be comprehensively elucidated solely through individual characteristics. The critical perspectives of this academic institution examine the concept of crime in conjunction with the societal, economic, and cultural contexts in which it occurs. Within this particular environment, the impact of social variables on criminal behavior assumes a significant significance. Hence, the French school of sociology of crime places emphasis on comprehending crime as a social phenomenon and advocates for comprehensive approaches that consider social structure and interactions in the endeavor to combat crime. Sociological views pertaining to crime underscore the strong association between crime and social circumstances, social organization, and interpersonal dynamics, rather than attributing it primarily to individual internal traits. Rather than centering on the psychological and personal attributes of the criminal individual as an explanation for the occurrence of crime, these theories highlight how the structural and social configurations of society might influence criminal inclinations. Within this particular framework, sociological theories pertaining to crime propose that crime ought to be

comprehended not solely as the aberrant actions of people, but also as a phenomenon intricately linked to the social environment and conditions in which it occurs.

The French school of sociology of crime, led by Alexander Lacassagne and Gabriel Tarde, adopts a critical perspective positing that crime is a consequence of social circumstances. Lacassagne posits that the primary factors contributing to criminal activity stem from societal disarray and pervasive corruption, whereas Tarde contends that criminal behavior emerges as a consequence of individuals copying prevailing social norms. These theories have demonstrated that crime is intricately linked to social structure and social relationships, highlighting that the explanation for criminal behavior cannot just rely on the internal attributes of the individual.

According to Özgül Dönmezer, the focal point of sociological approaches in criminology lies predominantly inside the United States. During the latter part of the 19th century and the early part of the 20th century, there was a progressive rise in the significance attributed to sociological theories in order to comprehend the underlying factors contributing to criminal activity and conduct (Dönmezer, 1981: 102). During this particular era, American sociologists conducted significant research in the realm of criminology, with a specific emphasis on examining the influence of social structure and social interactions on criminal behavior. The field of criminology experienced significant growth and recognition in the United States as it emerged as a prominent area of study within sociology departments. According to sociologists, crime is regarded as a social phenomenon, with its causes being attributed to social conditions and social structure rather than inherent individual traits. From this standpoint, it is underscored that the comprehension of crime should encompass not alone the aberrant conduct of the person, but also the phenomena itself, which necessitates an examination of the societal context and conditions. One aspect explored by American sociologists in the field of crime studies is to the correlation between fluctuations in crime rates and shifts in social structure or social organization. This discourse examines the impact of various social conditions on crime rates, including cultural conflict, competition, social stratification, physical and social mobility, population density and composition, political, religious, and economic ideologies, unemployment, and the distribution of income and employment. These studies have yielded significant insights into the impact of alterations in social structure on crime rates. Since the early 1900s, there has been an increased focus on the correlation between shifts in social class and crime rates. Sociologists have taken into account several aspects, including poverty, educational attainment, and access to social opportunities, while analyzing the influence of social class on the likelihood of engaging in criminal behavior. Within this particular

framework, scholars have posited that there exists a correlation between economic and social disparities and criminal behavior. Another field of inquiry has focused on elucidating the factors that contribute to the development of criminal behavior in individuals. Sociologists have directed their attention towards the phenomenon of law-abiding individuals transitioning into criminal behavior and have undertaken an examination of social learning theories in order to gain insight into this transformative process. The aforementioned ideas encompass various concepts, including imitation, attitude-value, frustration and hostility, reinforcement-support, and differential connection. The significance of social interactions and learning processes in comprehending the involvement of individuals in criminal behavior has been underscored.

The contributions made by American sociologists in the field of criminology have significantly contributed to the comprehension of criminal etiology and the development of effective strategies for its management. Sociologists have underscored the significance of examining the social context of crime, asserting that addressing crime necessitates a focus on the collective rather than the individual level. In the present context, their contributions have facilitated the enhancement and equitable transformation of crime-fighting strategies and judicial systems through the incorporation of considerations pertaining to the social structure of criminal behavior, social connections, and economic circumstances. Consequently, the establishment of the American school of sociology has garnered significant recognition within the realm of criminology, providing a crucial theoretical framework for comprehending the societal underpinnings of criminal behavior. Sociological techniques have emerged as prominent frameworks for implementing multifaceted and inclusive strategies in addressing criminal activities. Hence, sociological theories on crime have contributed to the development of more efficient and enduring strategies in combating illegal activities, as they prioritize not only the examination of individual criminal conduct but also the analysis of societal structures and conditions. The examination of sociological theories pertaining to crime has been essential in comprehending the underlying factors and dissemination of criminal behavior. These theories adopt an alternative perspective by acknowledging the significance of societal variables that elicit criminal conduct, as opposed to categorizing individuals as criminals or non-criminals only based on their biological and psychological attributes. Based on this particular perspective, it is posited that criminal conduct exhibits variability contingent upon temporal and spatial factors. Moreover, it is argued that the explanation of crime should not solely rely on the internal attributes of the individual, but rather necessitates an association with societal circumstances and the overarching social framework (Thio et al., 2013).

Sociological theories place significant emphasis on the notion that endeavors to comprehend the underlying factors contributing to criminal behavior have a direct impact on the formulation of policies aimed at addressing and mitigating crime. Previous research has indicated that sociological theories play a crucial role in comprehending the underlying factors behind individuals' engagement in criminal or deviant behaviors within society, as well as in formulating appropriate sanctions and strategies to address criminal activities (Kartal and Yaylacı, 2013: 183; İçli, 2014: 510-511). Sociological theories present distinct viewpoints within the field of criminology in contrast to alternative ideas on crime and criminality (Dolu, 2013). Consequently, there exists a considerable proliferation of sociological ideas pertaining to crime. The observation of sociological theories reveals that they concentrate on distinct areas and present diverse perspectives due to the intricate and multifaceted nature of the criminal problem. A multitude of sociological crime theories have emerged as a result of the presence of diverse types of crime, societal influences, and individual traits (Kızmaz, 2005). Hence, it is imperative to recognize that a comprehensive theoretical framework capable of elucidating the multifaceted nature of crime has not yet been established. While there exist notable distinctions among sociological theories pertaining to crime and criminality, these theories also have commonalities that hold significance in modern discourse and provide valuable guidance. The shared characteristics of these ideas can be highlighted based on six fundamental foundations (Carrabine et al., 2009).

Crime is a pervasive phenomenon that is inherent to all societies and poses significant challenges in terms of eradication. In certain instances, it can potentially contribute to the preservation of social order through the execution of specific functions.

Crime is frequently linked to instances of conflict. This conflict is associated with social stratification, vested interests, and notably economic determinants.

Crime is commonly linked to the presence of social tension, pressure, and stress. It is commonly linked to instances of deviating from societal norms, frequently characterized by concepts such as anomie, non-conformity, and social disorder.

Crime is intricately linked to the urban lifestyle of contemporary cities. Crime zones are formed as a result of the interplay between the conventions, values, and habits prevalent in metropolitan settings, as well as the criminal and non-criminal lifestyles that exist within diverse cultural surroundings.

The acquisition of criminal behavior is facilitated by the process of cultural transmission, wherein individuals acquire knowledge and adopt beliefs related to crime based on their prior experiences and cultural influences.

Crime is a consequence of non-compliance with legal statutes and societal norms, as well as a lack of effective social regulation.

Within this particular setting, numerous ideas have been posited in order to comprehend and elucidate the underlying factors contributing to criminal behavior. The primary determinant influencing the development of these ideas is the unequal applicability of the evolving and dynamic global structure across different societies. The phenomenon of crime is influenced by several economic, political, social, and cultural processes, as noted by Taşkın and Yılmaz (2020). Within this particular context, the theoretical perspectives on crime and criminality encompass theoretical frameworks that are influenced by the consequences of social change and transformation and evolve in alignment with the distinctive attributes of various cultures.

Broken Windows Theory:

The aforementioned theory posits a correlation between criminal activity and the condition of the physical surroundings, hence proposing a discernible mechanism for the proliferation of crime. The Broken Windows theory posits that the presence of minor transgressions and abnormalities can undermine societal norms, hence fostering an environment conducive to heightened criminal activity. This idea facilitates our comprehension of the social ramifications of criminal behavior and the influence of the surrounding environment on the occurrence of crime. The examination of the correlation between social order and crime holds significant importance within the realm of sociological theories. Within this particular setting, the Broken Windows Theory emerges as a theoretical framework that posits a correlation between the proliferation of criminal activity and the presence of social disorder and environmental elements. The Broken Windows Theory was formulated in 1982 by James Q. Wilson and George L. Kelling in their publication titled "The Atlantic." The essay titled "Broken Windows," which was published in a monthly magazine, presented the following proposition. This

hypothesis posits that the presence of environmental order and security significantly influences the emergence and dissemination of criminal behavior.

Kelling, the progenitor of the Broken Windows Theory, specifically focused on the escalation of criminal activity and societal disarray in urban areas like New York during the latter part of the 1960s in formulating this theoretical framework. The hypothesis acquired further significance in light of the emergence of "common crime" and the depopulation of urban cores throughout the 1980s. The Broken Windows Theory provides a significant framework for comprehending the underlying factors contributing to criminal behavior, namely by examining the intricate interplay between crime and the maintenance of societal order. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge the multifaceted and intricate nature of crime while discussing the controversies surrounding its execution and consequences. Furthermore, it is imperative to underscore the necessity for a more comprehensive and thorough approach, in addition to the insights offered by this theory. The Broken Windows Theory is a significant framework that highlights the influence of environmental order and social security on the development and diffusion of criminal behavior. It provides a comprehensive comprehension of the intricacies of crime within the social milieu. Based on the premises of this theoretical framework, prompt, and efficient intervention in instances of social disorder has the potential to mitigate the proliferation of criminal activities. Social phenomena refer to the various patterns and behaviors that occur within a society. These phenomena encompass the maintenance of norms and values plays a pivotal role in the mitigation of criminal behavior (Wilson- Kelling , 1982). The Broken Windows Theory has encountered criticism due to its limited focus on physical environmental issues. According to this critical approach, criminal behavior is influenced not only by the physical environment but also by the social environment. It is also associated with aspects such as people' degrees of social, economic, and educational attainment. In addition to the impact of geographical location on crime rates, the living conditions and social elements experienced by individuals can also have influence on the prevalence of criminal activities. Critics argue that the Broken Windows Theory fails to account for the underlying social, economic, and psychological factors that contribute to crime. According to Raudenbush (1999), it has been argued that relying solely on the physical environment is inadequate for explaining social instability.

Rational Choice Theory:

The comprehension of individuals' motivation for engaging in criminal activities is significantly enhanced with the application of rational choice theory. According to this theoretical perspective, criminal behavior arises from individuals' rational assessment of the costs and benefits associated with engaging in illegal activities. When the potential advantages of engaging in illegal activities outweigh the associated hazards, individuals may resort to criminal behavior. The analysis of this theory facilitates comprehension of the correlation between crime and individual decision-making. Rational Choice Theory, also referred to as Rational Choice Theory, originated from the concepts of rationality and reason that evolved during the Age of Enlightenment. Scholars such as Thomas Hobbes, Adam Smith, and Jeremy Bentham have significantly contributed to the development and application of Rational Choice Theory across several scientific disciplines (Sutton, 2001). According to several scholarly sources, the discipline in which the theory initially originated is economics, and Adam Smith is often regarded as the trailblazer of this theory (Boudon, 1998).

Smith's scholarly publication, titled "On National Wealth," comprises a collection of discussions pertaining to the concept of rationality (Boudon, 2003; Blume & Easley, 2008). However, the precise nature of these conversations remains rather ambiguous. The idea of Utilitarianism Ethics, sometimes known as Utilitarianism, has seen significant development, maturation, and acceptance within the field of behavioral sciences. The realization of this concept can be attributed to a considerable degree to the contributions made by the philosopher Jeremy Bentham, who is often associated with it. The philosopher introduced the notion of utility as a psychological construct that can be quantified by an individual's subjective well-being. Additionally, the philosopher proposed the idea of "pleasure calculation" (also known as hedonic calculation), asserting that individuals are inherently driven by the pursuit of pleasure and avoidance of pain, and that their choices are influenced by the maximization of inner happiness (utility). Lewin (1996) asserted that they presented it in a manner conducive to its provision. Gary Becker, the recipient of the 1992 Nobel Prize in economics, emerged as a prominent advocate of Rational Choice Theory. In his seminal work, Becker (1993) examined the concept of rationality via a behavioral lens, thereby introducing the application of this theory not just within the realm of economics, but also across several disciplines such as political science, sociology, social psychology, and criminology. Rational Choice Theory posits that individuals, referred to as actors, engage in a decision-making process that is guided by

rationality. The concept of rationality is manifested through the process of decision-making, wherein individuals evaluate the potential benefits to be obtained from a certain course of action in relation to the associated costs. Individuals strive to maximize their gains while simultaneously minimizing their losses (sacrifices). The fundamental premise of the theory stated by Tversky and Kahneman (1981) is as follows. Individuals select the alternative that they find most preferable. When an individual perceives no discernible distinction between several alternatives, they proceed by eliminating the possibilities that are least preferred. Subsequently, they either select one of the most favored options or opt not to make a decision. Three distinct preference scenarios can be delineated based on the aforementioned presuppositions (McClennen, 1990). One of the initial critiques of the concept pertains to its exclusive consideration of instantaneous time, hence rendering it static in nature. Individuals engage in decision-making processes that encompass not only immediate circumstances, but also take into account long-term implications. Dynamic Decision Theory was developed as a reaction to this critique. This model is predicated on the principle of utility maximization, with the added feature of incorporating utility maximization for future periods. The aforementioned paradigm has emerged as a significant component within theories of accumulation and investment, particularly within the domains of economics and finance (McClennen, 1990). The second critique of Rational Choice Theory pertains to the cognitive mechanisms involved in information processing. Assessing several alternatives may initially pose minimal challenges; but, as the quantity of options escalates, the process of making a decision gets increasingly arduous. The aforementioned objections played a significant role in the evolution and formulation of the theoretical construct known as "bounded rationality". Herbert A. Simon introduced the notion of constrained rationality in 1955. Simon argues that the human physiology possesses inherent limitations that extend to the cognitive capacity necessary for rational decision-making.

One notable critique of the idea pertains to its deficiency in providing sufficient information. In response to this critique, Simon (1955) introduced the concept of the bounded rationality model. The strategic decision-making process is another area where the fundamental rational choice model has faced criticism and subsequent refinement. It is assumed that the decision maker possesses independence from both the surrounding environment and other decision makers. Nevertheless, it is imperative for decision makers to consider the perspectives and actions of other decision makers when making their own conclusions. The aforementioned critique gave rise to the emergence of a novel theoretical framework. A significantly more intricate rational

decision-making process arises in the strategic setting and pertains to the field of Game Theory (Bernheim, 1986). However, it is important to note that within the field of Game Theory, decision makers are typically assumed to make decisions based on rationality. In response to the critique that Rational Choice Theory is deficient in addressing decision-making in conditions of risk, scholars have developed Prospect Theory (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979; Levy, 1997). This theory pertains to scenarios in which several options, such as financial investments, are linked to outcomes that are characterized by uncertainty. The importance lies in individuals' assessment of the potential outcomes of success or failure, and their subsequent pursuit of the most advantageous outcome. One notable critique of Rational Choice Theory is to the assumption that individuals consistently exhibit self-interested behavior and exclusively prioritize their own interests (Sen, 1977). The theory's perceived inadequacy in adequately considering human emotions remains unresolved, leading to a decline in its influence and diminished prominence in contemporary discourse. Notwithstanding these critiques and diverse reassessments, the use of the idea across many academic fields has witnessed a notable surge. According to MacDonald (2003: 551), Rational Choice Theory is currently seeing rapid growth and widespread adoption as a theoretical framework within the field of political science. The application of economic theory to the field of political science has given rise to the concept of "Public Choice Theory." This theoretical framework is employed to examine and understand the actions and decision-making processes of various actors within the political system, including bureaucrats, politicians, and voters. This exemplifies the influence of theoretical frameworks within the field of social sciences.

Routine Activities Theory:

According to this theoretical perspective, criminal behavior may manifest when individuals encounter possibilities that emerge within the context of their everyday routines. This statement underscores the correlation between criminal behavior and the circumstances in which both the offender and possible victim find themselves. The analysis of this theory facilitates comprehension of the manner in which crime is impacted by temporal, spatial, and situational aspects. The Routine Activities Theory (RAT) presents an alternative viewpoint in contrast to conventional criminological methodologies, contending that the prevention of crime can be achieved via the resolution of the underlying mechanisms that contribute to its occurrence.

This theoretical framework endeavors to elucidate the manifestation of criminal behavior by directing attention towards the criminal event per se, as opposed to emphasizing the personal attributes of the perpetrator. The routine activity theory, as conceptualized by Cohen and Felson, centers on three key elements: the lack of a prospective perpetrator, the presence of a vulnerable target, and the existence of an effective guardian (Bottoms and Wiles, 1997). The convergence of these three factors is necessary for the commission of illegal acts. Routine activity theory is grounded in the rational choice framework, which is also employed in situational crime prevention strategies. Like any other theoretical framework, routine activity theory is not exempt from criticism. One of the primary critiques revolves around the underlying assumption that individuals engaged in illicit activities exhibit rationality in their decision-making processes. The individual responsible for executing the security measures may employ a different line of reasoning than that of others. The individuals in question may lack awareness on the implementation of situational crime prevention techniques. Individuals may potentially be affected by substances such as drugs or alcohol or may choose to disregard safety measures for assorted reasons.

Differential Association Theory

The Differential Attribution Theory (DAT) is a sociological framework that seeks to elucidate the causes and motivations behind criminal conduct and the occurrence of crime. According to the theoretical framework under consideration, the primary determinant of criminal behavior is attributed to the disparities in relational dynamics and possibilities experienced by individuals. The idea established by Edwin Sutherland in 1947 contends that criminal behavior is a result of social interactions among individuals. The Differential Attribution Theory (DAT) is a theoretical framework aimed at elucidating the underlying factors contributing to criminal behavior within the framework of interpersonal interactions and disparities in opportunities. The hypothesis proposed by Edwin Sutherland introduced a novel viewpoint to approaches in combating crime, highlighting that criminal behavior and the occurrence of crime are outcomes stemming from social interactions. The concept of Differential Attribution Theory (DAT), also referred to as Differential Attribution-Reinforcement, was initially introduced by Edwin Sutherland, a sociological criminologist, in 1947. Sutherland aimed to organize the extensive array of knowledge surrounding criminal behavior and establish a comprehensive theory of crime causation, as elucidated by Cressey (1952). The publication by Vold and Bernard (1988)

aimed to present theoretical perspectives. The Differential Association Theory (DAT) is intricately connected to the Social Learning Theory, positing that criminal conduct is acquired through interpersonal exchanges. The Differential Association Theory (DAT) elucidates the fundamental origins of criminal behavior by examining several aspects, including crime-specific strategies, criminal incentives, and justifications for transgressing legal norms. The author contends that the aforementioned factors ought to be ascribed to the social contexts and interactions of individuals, rather than their genetic origins.

Social Learning Theory

It has a similar perspective. According to this theory, individuals learn by observing the behavior of other people around them. Criminal behavior is learned in this way by individuals observing individuals engaging in criminal behavior and understanding their unique techniques, motivations, and justifications. In this way, individuals learn the factors that lead to crime and can repeat these behaviors (Jeffery , 1965; Matsueda , 2006; Reid , 2003; Sutherland , 1947; Vold and Bernard, 1986).

Tension Theory:

Another theory associated with Differential Association Theory (DAT) is General Tension Theory. This theory attributes the root cause of crime to “the failure of institutions, families, and other structures to meet the functional and emotional needs of individuals” (Donegan and Danon , 2008 ; p. 4). This can lead individuals to develop feelings of personal alienation, which can lead to antisocial behavior or even criminal acts. According to General Strain Theory, criminal behavior is seen as an individual response to external sources of stress or pressure (Akers , 2000; Colvin , Cullen , & Vander Ven, 2002). Strain theory, which suggests that social conflicts and inequalities are the main cause of crime, states that crime is caused by social It emphasizes that it is closely related to the structure. It states that crime may occur when society does not provide sufficient opportunities and equality to individuals. Examining this theory helps us understand how crime is linked to social inequalities. Strain theory can be used “to illuminate the problem of structurally determined tension and conflict in organizations ” (Pettigrew , 1968 ; p. 206). For example, in the law enforcement context, there may be situations

where cultural fidelity is important, direct supervision is lacking or non-existent, and role demands are constantly changing with uncertainty (Kennedy and Kennedy, 1972; Maahs and Pratt, 2001).

Similarly, within a scientific community, an auditor's desire to maintain scientific integrity may conflict with professional and institutional pressures (Dorey , 2010 ; Martinson , Anderson, & de Vries , 2005). Role Strain is also important as part of this theory. This concept suggests that individuals experience difficulty trying to fulfill competing or conflicting role demands (Goode , 1960 ; Hecht , 2001 ; and Kennedy & Kennedy, 1972). Specifically, it results in increased individual strain when “the demands associated with one role directly interfere with an individual's ability to meet the demands of another role” (Hecht , 2001 ; p. 112).

Integrated Guilt Theory:

The sociological theory offered by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1990) aims to comprehend the fundamental origins of criminal behavior. This theory emphasizes the significance of individual attributes and opportunities in elucidating criminal conduct. The fundamental premise of the theory posits that a primary determinant of criminal activity is a diminished level of self-control. The comprehension of criminal conduct is significantly enhanced via the application of integrated criminality theory, which examines the influence of biological, psychological, and social elements. This theory places significant emphasis on the notion that the etiology of criminal behavior is characterized by a multitude of factors that are intricate and intricate in nature. The examination of this hypothesis is crucial for comprehending the influence of genetic predispositions, personality traits, and environmental circumstances on the development of criminal behavior. The foundation of Integrated Guilt Theory rests upon two primary concepts: The relationship between self-control and opportunities. The fundamental concept underlying this theory posits that persons with diminished levels of self-control are more prone to engaging in illegal activities. Self-control can be operationally defined as an individual's capacity to regulate and govern their own actions and behaviors. Individuals with diminished levels of self-control may have a tendency to disregard long-term objectives in favor of immediate satisfaction. These factors may contribute to the manifestation of criminal conduct, a proclivity for engaging in risky behaviors, and a desire for immediate satisfaction. According to the theoretical framework, opportunities for engaging in criminal action manifest when the

circumstances facilitate an environment that is characterized by ease and minimal danger. Hirschi and Gottfredson (2017) suggest that the convergence of these two notions gives rise to criminal behavior. Individuals with diminished levels of self-control exhibit a propensity towards immediate gratification and are more like to participate in dangerous behaviors, including criminal activities. Simultaneously, the presence of low-security chances facilitates the commission of criminal activities.

Subcultural theories

These ideas aim to elucidate the criminal behavior and deviance exhibited by individuals who are members of the lower socioeconomic class within society. These theories typically analyze child and youth gangs, with a specific emphasis on the values, norms, and behavioral patterns exhibited by these collectives. Albert K. Cohen, a prominent scholar in the field, has made significant contributions to the realm of sociological theories. His subculture theory draws heavily from the works of Durkheim and Merton, particularly their concept of "Anomie." The subculture theory posits that instances of criminal behavior arise when there is a clash between the prevailing social order and values, and the ideals embraced by individuals belonging to lower-income groups. Cohen's seminal work, "Delinquent," was first published in 1955. In his scholarly publication entitled "Boys," the author examines the delinquent conduct exhibited by adolescent males hailing from socioeconomically disadvantaged backgrounds and affiliated with gang collectives. Cohen posits that the attainment of success and prosperity, sometimes referred to as the "American Dream," presents formidable challenges for persons of lower socioeconomic status within American society. The aforementioned scenario gives rise to a divergence in values among the persons involved, subsequently resulting in the emergence of a subculture and the proliferation of criminal conduct (Tierney, 2010). According to Cohen, the "American way of life" can be characterized as a societal structure wherein individuals strive to attain certain objectives, which prove to be particularly challenging for those belonging to the lower socioeconomic class. The argument posits that membership in a certain group heightens the inclination towards engaging in criminal activities among its constituents. This particular subculture manifests distinct norms and values that diverge from the prevailing societal ideals, perhaps providing a basis for the justification of criminal conduct. Cohen's theoretical framework posits that criminal behavior arises as a manifestation of subcultural

influences, with young individuals engaging in such actions as a response to societal factors. They also exhibit their dedication to their subculture (Cohen, 1995).

Social control theory

The significance of social control theory has increased since the latter part of the 19th century. Emile Durkheim conducted an analysis on the mechanisms through which social order is established and underscored the significance of social control. Durkheim posits that the norms, values, and institutions within a given community serve as guiding mechanisms for individuals, facilitating a structured framework that safeguards social order. The social control theory underwent significant advancements during the 1960s, leading to the establishment of a comprehensive framework for comprehending criminal behavior and deviant actions. Travis Hirschi's theoretical framework, commonly referred to as "Bond Theory" or "Social Bond Theory," endeavors to elucidate the influence of social relationships on people's propensity for engaging in criminal behavior. Hirschi posits that the presence of social bonds, encompassing familial, educational, occupational, and institutional connections, serves to diminish proclivities towards criminal behavior by fostering a heightened inclination to adhere to societal conventions (Korkmaz, 2020; Wilson, 2001).

In contrast, Michel Foucault introduced a distinct viewpoint to the theory of social control by examining the concepts of social control and power throughout the mid-20th century. Foucault conducts an analysis of the interplay between power and knowledge, elucidating how these forces contribute to the functioning of social control mechanisms. Furthermore, he explores the implications of this framework for comprehending the nature of crime. The social control theory is a theoretical framework that analyzes the methods employed to govern the conduct of individuals, with the aim of upholding societal order and stability. This theoretical framework aims to elucidate the factors influencing individuals' decisions to comply with societal norms or engage in criminal behavior. The social control theory seeks to elucidate the occurrence of criminal behavior by considering not only the culpability of an individual but also the influence of societal conditions. The perspectives offered by Michel Foucault provide an alternative lens through which to examine social control theory. Michel Foucault established the notion of the panopticon during his examination of the mechanisms through which power relations and the control of information operate inside society. The term "Panopticon" denotes an architectural

configuration characterized by a central watchtower, from which the surrounding captives housed in cells can be subjected to constant surveillance. According to Foucault (2003), the panopticon's impact on contemporary cultures was observed by him, who understood it as a mechanism of social control that induces individuals to experience a perpetual state of monitoring.

Stigma Theory

The idea of labeling, which emerged within the paradigm of symbolic interactionism, serves as a foundation for comprehending the occurrence of social deviance and criminal behavior. The theoretical underpinnings of this framework were established throughout the mid-20th century, coinciding with a growing interest in understanding the causes and manifestations of social deviance and criminal behavior. The theoretical foundation of this study draws upon the works of prominent sociologists, namely Emile Durkheim and Georg Simmel. Durkheim endeavored to elucidate the occurrence of deviance from societal standards and the phenomenon of crime by positing the hypothesis that heightened social density engenders a decline in moral density. Intellectuals of this era endeavored to comprehend the mechanisms of social control and the significance of upholding societal norms. "Sociology of Deviance" as a seminal work in the field. This book, published in 1963, explores the concept of deviance and its social construction. Becker's research delves into the labeling process and how individuals come to be labeled as deviant by society. Through his analysis, he highlights the role of social interactions and power dynamics in the creation and maintenance of deviant identities. Becker's work has had a significant impact on the field of sociology, providing valuable insights into the social construction of deviance and the implications of labeling on individuals and society. Through the publication of his work titled "Sociology of Deviance" (Hariciler: Studies on the Sociology of Deviance), the author effectively disseminated the theory of labeling to a broader readership. Becker posited that the etiology of crime and deviant acts cannot be only attributed to individual subjective inclinations, but rather, the labeling and societal reactions also exert considerable influence in molding these behaviors. The year 1960. During the 1970s and 1980s, the labeling theory gained recognition as a significant perspective within the realm of crime and deviance.

The theoretical framework proposed by Edwin Lemert, encompassing the notions of "Primary Deviation" and "Secondary Deviation," has exerted considerable influence in the advancement

of the field. Primary deviation pertains to the initial act of deviation exhibited by an individual, whereas secondary deviation elucidates the subsequent alterations in the individual's conduct due to the labeling and reactions of society. Prominent scholars in the field of theory including notable individuals such as Frank Tannenbaum, Kai Erikson, Adwin M. Lamert, and Edwin M. Schur (Bal, 2008; Becker, 2018).

Feminist Theories

The examination of crime through the lens of feminist theory facilitates a deeper comprehension of the intricate interplay between gender and different dimensions of criminal behavior. Feminist theories endeavor to make a meaningful contribution towards the establishment of a more equitable society through the examination of gender disparities and the interconnectedness between social norms and criminal behavior. The many methodologies employed by these ideas provide a wider and more inclusive vantage point on matters pertaining to crime and gender. (Çaha, 1996; Slattery, 2011; Taşkın & Yılmaz, 2020). Feminist theories encompass a range of perspectives that seek to comprehensively examine the intersections of crime and gender, offering nuanced analyses of these complex topics. In her seminal work published in 1948, Carol Smart examines the intricate relationship between women and crime. The author's book, titled "Criminology," undertakes an analysis of the factors that contribute to women's involvement in criminal activities, while also exploring the influence of gender on criminal behavior patterns. Additionally, she conducts an analysis of the societal perception of women involved in illegal activities and explores the impact of gender norms on their experiences. In her seminal work titled "The Female Offender: Girls, Women, and Oaths," Meda Chesney-Lind (1948) explores the subject of female criminality. In her scholarly research titled "Crime", the author examines the factors that contribute to female involvement in criminal activities, as well as their distinctive patterns of criminal behavior. Additionally, she examines the effects of the criminal system on women. In her seminal work published in 1951, Kathleen Daly explores the intricate relationship between gender and crime. Furthermore, in her scholarly publication entitled "Punishment," the author examines the victimization of women in relation to criminal activities, as well as delving into the underlying factors that drive women to engage in such behaviors. The author highlights the issue of gender discrimination within the justice system.

Individual Crime Theories

The development and utilization of individual crime theories have held significant historical significance in elucidating the underlying meaning and causal factors of criminal behavior. The initial ideas sought to ascribe the genesis of criminal behavior to a singular causative factor. Could you please provide more context or specify what you are referring to? The individual stated that various elements, including mental illness, socioeconomic disadvantage, and physical attributes, may contribute to criminal behavior. However, recent studies have demonstrated that crime is a complex phenomenon (İçli, 2007). The examination of individual crime theories is typically categorized into four primary areas. The aforementioned titles encompass Classical School Theories, Neo-Classical School Theory, Positivist School, and Geographical School.

The Classical School of criminological theories posits that criminal behavior is mostly a consequence of individual decision-making. Criminal offenders engage in a decision-making process wherein they weigh the prospective benefits against the likelihood of facing legal consequences. The Neo-Classical School Theory, derived from classical theories, acknowledges the influence of individual psychological, societal, and economic elements in the perpetration of criminal behavior. The Positivist School posits that crime is influenced by various causes, including biological, psychological, and societal elements. Numerous factors, including biological predisposition, IQ level, and personality structure, can exert an influence on an individual's propensity for engaging in criminal behavior. The spatial School is an analytical framework that examines the relationship between crime and spatial conditions. The statement underscores the concentration of crime rates within specific geographical areas and highlights the influence of socio-economic factors on the prevalence of criminal activity. Cesare Beccaria (1738-1794) expounded upon his significant ideas regarding crime and punishment in his seminal work titled "On Crimes and Punishments". Beccaria conducted an investigation into the underlying causes of criminal behavior and posited that the act of committing a crime is a product of rational decision-making. According to him, sanctions should be deterrent and proportionate. He underlined that punishments should be imposed in accordance with the general interest of the public and that the penalty should be determined with the consent of the

public. He also claimed that harsh punishments that are not appropriate to the offense committed are not beneficial in curbing crime. Jeremy Bentham (1748-1832) adopted the philosophical method termed utilitarianism . According to him, sanctions should be tailored to deliver the most benefit for the prevention of crime and the welfare of society. Bentham maintained that the penal system should be constructed logically in order to dissuade the criminal and safeguard society. He also underlined that a transparent penal system should be built in a way that will attract the public's trust. Adolphe Quetelet , Guerry and Montesquieu believed that the phenomenon of crime is affected by extrinsic factors such as geographical location and climatic circumstances. The geographical school states that these factors affect crime rates and criminal conduct may vary between various places. For example, it claims that variables such as climate, wind, temperature, and soil qualities have an impact on humans. Therefore, he argues that geographical considerations should be taken into consideration while evaluating criminal conduct (Dönmezer, 1994:158-160). Using recent crime statistics obtained in France in 1827, Guerry proved that crime was linked to socioeconomic variables. It has been proven that there is an inverse association between education level and crime and that the effect of population density on crime is considerable (Adler et al., 1991 ; Akpınar, 2018).

Psychological Theories of Crime

Psychological crime theories adopt an approach that seeks to identify the underlying causes of crime inside the psychological makeup of individuals. Based on these theoretical perspectives, criminal conduct is believed to stem from intrinsic elements, encompassing people' cognitive processes, affective states, early life encounters, and dispositional characteristics. These theories aim to comprehend the phenomena of crime by an examination of the psychological and cognitive processes within individuals who engage in criminal behavior. The psychoanalytic approach developed by Sigmund Freud aims to elucidate the structure of human cognition by delineating three fundamental components of the mind: the id, ego, and superego. The concept of the id can be understood as the manifestation of an insatiable animalistic nature within individuals, representing their selfish and impulsive tendencies that prioritize immediate demands. The ego endeavors to maintain equilibrium between the id and the external surroundings, while also governing the impulses in alignment with both the environment and established societal norms. The superego is a psychological construct that encompasses moral principles and standards, serving as a guiding force for individuals. According to Freud

(Karaosmanoğlu, 2002), the human mind formation is influenced by these three components. August Aichorn emerged as a pioneering figure within the field of psychology when he embarked upon an investigation of criminal conduct via the lens of psychoanalytic ideas. According to his perspective, humans possess inherently asocial personalities from birth. Nevertheless, individuals initiate the process of socialization through their interactions with the surrounding environment. According to Aichorn, the challenges encountered throughout these transitions have the potential to contribute to the development of antisocial disorders and criminal behavior. The pleasure phase and the reality phase are significant stages within this particular process. Moreover, it is worth noting that while certain individuals may possess inherent criminal tendencies, others may resort to engaging in criminal activities by opportunistically awaiting favorable circumstances (Dolu et al., 2012:39-40). Psychological theories of crime aim to comprehend the internal tensions, emotional challenges, and intellectual impairments experienced by those involved in criminal behavior. Based on these theoretical perspectives, criminal conduct is posited as a response stemming from the internal psychological landscape of the individual. Nonetheless, the psychoanalytic approach has faced criticism due to the inherent limitations of its notions, such as id, ego, and superego, which lack empirical testability and quantifiability. Furthermore, a restricted number of individuals with psychiatric disorders have been subjected to the use of the psychoanalysis technique (Dolu, 2010:180). Psychological crime theories also encompass the examination of general personality qualities and their relationship to criminal behavior. The presence of aggression and assertiveness in an individual has the potential to heighten their inclination towards engaging in acts of violence and criminal behavior. Psychopathic characteristics have the potential to exert an influence on criminal conduct. Moreover, criminal behavior has been found to be linked to mental disorders such as psychosis and neurosis. According to Demirbaş (2001:112), when individuals experience psychosis, their vision of reality becomes distorted, leading to the occurrence of internal conflicts and psychological anguish in cases of neurosis. One of the subjects under investigation is the correlation between intellect and criminal behavior. There exists a positive correlation between lower levels of intelligence and an increased propensity for engaging in criminal behavior. Nevertheless, this association may prove inadequate in elucidating more intricate offenses like white-collar crimes. Moral development is a significant component that exhibits an association with criminal behavior. Kohlberg's theoretical framework on moral development elucidates the extent to which individuals have attained moral maturity and the subsequent impact of this development on their proclivity towards engaging in criminal behavior.

Alcohol and drug consumption are significant variables that influence criminal conduct. The consumption of alcohol and drugs has the potential to diminish an individual's volitional control and cognitive capacity, hence increasing the likelihood of engaging in criminal behavior. Offenses perpetrated while under the influence of such substances can encompass a spectrum of criminal acts, spanning from homicide to acts of violence. Due to its significance, the investigation of the correlation between alcohol and drug use and criminal behavior has emerged as a crucial field of study (Dönmezler, 1994).

Biological Crime Theories

Biological crime theories suggest that the primary determinant of criminal behavior stems from a range of pathological disorders and biological characteristics inherent in individuals. This hypothesis posits that persons who engage in criminal behavior possess biological characteristics that are deemed inferior compared to those who abstain from criminal activities. This theory was formulated on the basis of evolutionary theory. According to this particular perspective, those who engage in criminal behavior are regarded as "humanoid beings" who have yet to fully undergo the process of human evolution. These individuals are deemed inherently criminal, and the notion of intergenerational transmission of criminal behavior is embraced. Within this particular context, it is posited that genetic elements are implicated in the genesis of criminal behavior. During the 1950s, there was a notable proliferation of the notion that human conduct might be influenced by physical attributes. Franz Gall, a prominent figure in the field of phrenology, made significant contributions to the study of the human brain and the researcher's investigations into phenology, namely the study of cranial morphology, have yielded insights suggesting a correlation between individuals' brain shape and their behavioral tendencies. There exists a proposition positing a correlation between the degree of development exhibited by specific brain regions and an individual's personality traits and actions. Similarly, the perspective that conduct is influenced by brain chemistry and that hormones are linked to behaviors such as aggression garnered significant attention during this era. Cesare Lombroso's contributions to the field of criminology lie within the realm of biological theories. The works of Lombroso also hold significant scholarly value. Lombroso believed that individuals who engage in criminal behavior exhibit distinct physical attributes that distinguish them from non-offenders. The individual asserted that the aforementioned characteristics encompassed physical attributes, namely pertaining to cranial structure and

dental dimensions. Nevertheless, this perspective has faced criticism, as it has been acknowledged that crime can also be influenced by environmental factors and diseases. In addition, biological crime theories encompass genetic techniques as well. This strategy posits the acceptance of a crime gene and seeks to investigate the influence of genetic factors on criminal behavior through studies conducted on families and twins (Dolu et al., 2012).

CONCLUSION

This article provides an analysis of sociological ideas pertaining to crime and explores diverse theoretical frameworks aimed at comprehending the societal origins of criminal behavior. Sociological views on crime place emphasis on the notion that crime is not solely a product of individual decision-making, but rather, is influenced by various social forces that contribute to its production. These theoretical frameworks facilitate our comprehension of the etiology of criminal activities and the mechanisms via which criminal behavior might be rationalized.

Numerous studies have demonstrated a strong correlation between crime and other elements, including the social environment, economic situations, social class disparities, and family patterns. The field of criminology known as cartographic school focuses on analyzing the spatial patterns of crime, with an emphasis on understanding how crime is influenced by social factors. The French school of crime sociology posits a correlation between crime and social structure as well as economic disparities, whereas Italian criminal anthropology associate's criminality with biological elements.

RESTRICTION

The research is limited to scientific research that has been previously conducted around the world and published in the literature.

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RESOURCES

"A General Theory of Crime " by Travis Hirschi and Michael Gottfredson 2017 Macat Publications Amazon e-book.

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